

Enhanced group analysis and analytical solutions for the mode shapes of non-uniform rods

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Abstract:

Structural modeling of non-uniform cross-sections plays a crucial role in the vibration analysis of non-conventional elastic bodies and usually involves complicated differential equations (DEs). The difficulty in computing analytical solutions for such equations directs their resolution toward numerical approaches, which do not work for arbitrary material and geometric cross-section variations. Scarce analytical solutions are available in the literature for these problems, even considering particularly simple non-uniformities. Whereas numerical methods provide fruitful results for assessing the motion behavior of particular non-uniform-like structures with high sophistication, analytical solutions also offer notable benefits, e.g., avoiding convergence studies and approximation errors, reducing computational time, and inspecting problems with arbitrary elements such as undefined non-uniform cross-sections. Within the framework of finding analytical solutions, symmetry methods encompass changing coordinate procedures via group transformations for classifying, simplifying, and solving DEs. Among these methods, enhanced group analysis gives equivalence transformations for classifying and determining families of DEs that may be free of arbitrary parameters and constants or at least have fewer of them. It brings the benefit of dealing with simpler but mathematically equivalent equations, thus likely accomplishing their analytical solutions. This work deals with the computation of such equivalent equations and their solution via symmetry methods and power series for vibration models of rods with both material and geometric non-uniformities. These models follow the associated mode shape equations, which provide displacement patterns for the given vibrating systems. From that, an elegant way of deriving analytical solutions arises for non-uniform rod configurations.